

Exploration of near-infrared and short-term variability in spectra of planetary nebulae precursors

Version 2

Description

The Data Management Plan (DMP) is developed in the framework of the project No 5.2.1.1.i.0/2/24/I/CFLA/007 "Internal and External Consolidation of the University of Latvia" of the second round of the Consolidation and Governance Change Implementation Grants within Investment 5.2.1.1.i "Research, Development and Consolidation Grants" under Reform 5.2.1.r "Higher Education and Science Excellence and Governance Reform" of Reform and Investment Strand 5.2 of the Latvian Recovery and Resilience Mechanism Plan "Ensuring Change in the Governance Model of Higher Education Institutions", postdoctoral research grant project No. LU-BA-PG-2024/1-0020 "Exploration of near-infrared and short-term variability in spectra of planetary nebulae precursors" (project manager: Ph. D. Kārlis Puķītis, 1st September 2024 – 31st August 2025, 61 380.00 EUR).

Summary of the postdoctoral research grant project: Despite planetary nebulae being objects of great astrophysical use and interest, it is poorly understood how they take shape. It is unclear how spherically symmetric nebulae surrounding asymptotic giant branch phase stars become non-spherical upon arrival at the post-asymptotic giant branch stage - an immediate precursor to planetary nebula phase. The poorly understood stellar wind in the post-asymptotic giant branch stage is expected to play a significant role in the morphological change. High-resolution spectroscopy provides a way to investigate physical processes related to the stellar wind formation. Spectral line variability of stars that have recently started post-asymptotic giant branch evolution will be investigated by using spectra acquired with advanced spectrographs. The focus will be on two areas that

are virtually unexplored as of yet – variability in the near-infrared and short-term variability. The former will be studied by using already available spectra and will result in a scientific article. Observing time proposals will be prepared to provide additional spectra that will contribute to investigation of both types of variability. By allowing to probe dynamic processes in the region above the stellar surface where the stellar wind forms, such exploration has a potential to improve the knowledge about shaping of planetary nebulae.

Funder

European Commission | | EC

Grant

Internal and External
Consolidation of the University
of Latvia
(5.2.1.1.i.0/2/24/I/CFLA/007)

Researchers

Kārlis Puķītis (0000-0003-2599-6126)

Organizations

University of Latvia

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: Exploration of near-infrared and short-term variability in spectra of planetary nebulae precursors

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Organizations:

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: European Commission | EC

Grants: Internal and External Consolidation of the University of Latvia
(5.2.1.1.i.0/2/24/I/CFLA/007)

Project: Exploration of near-infrared and short-term variability in spectra of planetary nebulae precursors (LU-BA-PG-2024/1-0020)

3. License

License: CC-BY-4.0

Access Rights: Public

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4. Templates

Descriptions

High-resolution spectra of post-AGB stars

High-resolution time-resolved optical and near-infrared spectra of multiple post-asymptotic giant branch (post-AGB) stars are and will be observed.

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

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1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

Spectra of post-AGB stars are and will be observed in order to study dynamical processes in their atmospheres and shed some light on the formation of wind in this stage of stellar evolution. Observing time proposals were prepared for observations at Calar Alto observatory and Moléai Astronomical Observatory.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Observation data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

Others

Observed spectra will be stored in the FITS format

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

1

GB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

The spectra observed during this project will be complemented by spectra of the same stars observed earlier with the same or different instruments. These spectra will be downloaded from various freely accessible archives, for example, The Calar Alto Archive.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The spectra observed during this project will be useful for the astronomers that are interested in the specific stars that will be observed (for example, IRAS

Z02229+6208) or post-AGB stars in general.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

No

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

FITS (Flexible Image Transport System)

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

No

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

No

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

The observed spectra will be publicly available after a period of one year from the date on which observations were carried out.

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

DataverseLV

The spectra observed at the Calar Alto Observatory will be available in the Calar Alto Archive (<http://caha.sdc.cab.inta-csic.es/calto/>). Such archives are the most convenient place to store, look for, and download astronomical (observational) data. The spectra observed at the Molétai Astronomical Observatory will be uploaded to the repository DataverseLV (<https://dataverse.lv/>) since this observatory does not maintain an archive.

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Standard software for working with the FITS files are necessary to inspect the observed spectra, for example, IRAF, SAOImage DS9, or Astropy.

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

No

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

The spectra observed at the Calar Alto observatory will be freely available in the Calar Alto Archive. The only requirement for their usage is an appropriate acknowledgment. The spectra observed at the Molètai Astronomical Observatory will be freely available in the repository DataverseLV.

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

The first spectra will become publicly available on March 2026 and the last spectra - on December 2026. The observed spectra will remain re-usable permanently.

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

No

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Kārlis Puķītis (0000-0003-2599-6126)

Besides K. Puķītis downloading the data from the observatories after the observations and analyzing them, the data will be stored and made publicly available by the Calar Alto Archive and the repository DataverseLV.

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

Passwords

After the observations, it is possible to download the spectra from the observatory via password. During the analysis, the spectra will be stored in a password-

protected computer.

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

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